

One-stage and two-stage word recognition processes, revealed by multichannel MEG measurements

Victor Vvedensky¹, Vitaly Verkhlyutov ², Konstantin Gurtovoy¹.

¹ RNC Kurchatov Institute, Moscow, Russia

² Institute of Higher Nervous Activity and Neurophysiology of RAS, Moscow, Russia

VictorLvo@yandex.ru

Abstract. We measured magnetic signals of the human brain during recognition of spoken words and always see that MEG signal looks like a concatenation of oscillation episodes. In many cortical locations individual episodes coincide in time with word recognition process - from the sound onset to the button press confirming recognition. Sometimes the recognition occurs in two stages and one-stage and two-stage processes run simultaneously in different cortical sites. This holds for majority of cases with most frequently occurring recognition time. Very quick recognitions run in one stage, while very slow recognitions – in two stages. We believe that a synchronously operating set of neural populations spread over the cortex is involved in word recognition process and jointly makes a decision about which word the subject heard.

Keywords: Background Cortical Activity, Sharp Switches in Brain Waves, Word Recognition.

1. Introduction

Neural populations in different parts of the brain from time to time suddenly shift their mode of oscillation, changing amplitude, wave duration, wave shape or baseline drift. This is clearly visible in the brain EEG or MEG signals. This leads to the concept of a discrete temporal structure of the encephalographic signal [1, 2]. Continuous time series can be decomposed into the sequence of segments with readily detectable sharp borders. It's like breaking a continuous line into smooth sections connected by kinks. In our previous EEG experiments we observed that these segments often coincided in time with the process of single spoken word recognition [3]. We repeated this word recognition study on a multichannel magnetometer, which provides much better separation of the contributions of different active cortical areas to the signals recorded around the subject's head [4].

2. Methods

The MEG measurements were taken at the Center for Neurocognitive Research (MEG Center) of the Moscow City University of Psychology and Education using a helmet-shaped whole head 306-channel magnetometer (VectorView, Elekta Neuromag).

Sixteen volunteers took part in the study, 21 to 40 years old, 14 females, 2 males, everyone right handed. None of the participants had known neurological or psychiatric disorders or hearing deficit. All subjects signed an informed consent. The study was approved by the local ethics committee at the Institute of Higher Nervous Activity and Neurophysiology of Russian Academy of Science and was conducted following the ethical principles regarding human experimentation (Helsinki Declaration).

Before starting each experiment we determined the coordinates of anatomical reference points (left and right preauricular points and nasion) and locations of inductors, attached on the upper forehead and behind the auricles. We used the Fastrak three-dimensional digitization device (Polhemus). The signals from attached coils were used to compensate possible displacements of the subject's head in relation to the MEG sensors during measurements.

Magnetic brain responses were recorded with the sampling rate of 1000 Hz. Native hardware filters with band pass 0.1-330 Hz were used. The very low frequency (<0.5 Hz) signals and the 50-Hz power line interference and its harmonics were removed using the spatiotemporal signal separation (tSSS) method implemented in the MaxFilter program (Elekta Neuromag). The high signal-to-noise ratio provided by this measurement system made it possible to avoid narrow-band filtering and signal averaging. General data processing was done using the Brainstorm software [5].

During measurement, the subject was sitting in a magnetically shielded room. His (her) eyes were closed to avoid suppression of the alpha rhythm. The stimuli were pre-recorded words uttered by a human and delivered in earphones. The subject was instructed to recognize the heard word and to confirm recognition by a keystroke. Playback of the next word started 1 - 3 seconds after the button was pressed. In a single experiment every subject heard 80 words of the same sound duration and this measurement lasted for about 4 minutes. 8 different Russian adjectives were presented in this sequence, 10 times each in random order. Three different sets of eight adjectives close in their meaning with different word durations (680, 830, 910 ms) were presented to each subject. The choice of the particular adjectives was based on our previous experiments [6, 7], which produced highly reproducible results, provided that the group of words used in a short experiment were close in meaning. This in turn relies on the experimental findings [8], providing evidence that the semantically close words are mapped onto cortical surface in neighboring locations.

The measurement consisted of 80 alternating periods of perception of words and pauses between words. We processed signals from 204 channels, which measured gradients of the magnetic field generated by the brain. The gradient sensors are less susceptible to the distant sources and hence are more spatially selective. Each event of word recognition generated 204 different curves, which were arranged into the matrix, consisting of the columns, each containing 10 plots, as shown in Fig.1 and Fig.4. This was done for convenient visual inspection of the whole set of data in 204 channels.

3. Results: Sharp changes of the signal time course.

We arranged 2 seconds long epochs of the signal into the data matrix bringing together similar events. The signal time course during word recognition process is highlighted in color between vertical lines in Fig.1. For every subject and each perceived word there were 10-30 sensors where the signal wave-shape radically changes in the beginning and the end of the recognition. The signal between these time points often can be considered as a single oscillation episode (Fig.1, Panel A).

Fig. 1. MEG records of one subject during spoken word recognition. Panel A presents recognition events in 13 channels, where one-stage oscillation episode was observed. The episode is highlighted in blue. Panel B shows 19 episodes, split into two stages, highlighted in green and magenta. The number of each plot indicates the position of the corresponding sensor in the helmet surrounding the head, as shown in Fig.2. The rightmost vertical line indicates the instant, when the subject presses the button confirming recognition of the word heard. This happens 402 ms after word onset. That is much earlier than the sound of the word *petlyajuschij-winding* ends (680 ms). Duration of sound is shown by the magenta horizontal line.

In some other sensors the recognition period can be split into two-stages, as shown in the Panel B in Fig1. The signals may have different shape during recognition, even chaotic, though these one-stage and two stage events occur most often. The analysis of different types of oscillation episodes deserves special study, which is already done for large set of data [9]. Here we consider only these two, most significant in our

opinion, cases. Fig.2 shows positions of the sensors where one-stage and two-stage processes were recorded for this subject. The neural populations, generating these magnetic signals, are interspersed in the rear part of the brain. Each of these neural populations oscillates in its own manner during word recognition – this is manifested by the individual wave-shape of the signal in each sensor (Fig.1). Despite this diversity, all active cortical areas, located well apart, synchronously start and finish the current episode. The process of word recognition proceeds as a team-work of many local areas scattered over the cortex. This is consistent with the idea that the human words are mapped onto the cortex, as a set, scattered over the entire surface [8]. The process that retrieves a word from memory must also operate on the entire surface.

Fig. 2. The left and right rear views of the helmet with positions of sensors, where the signals shown in Fig.1 were recorded. Black arrows indicate direction of the subject's gaze. Blue compass needle arrows indicate sensors, where one-stage process was detected. Magenta-green arrows indicate locations where two-stage process was observed. Each arrow shows the direction of electric current in the neural tissue located under corresponding sensor. This current generates magnetic field.

The location and number of active areas involved in the recognition process varies from word to word. Each time a new configuration of neural populations is activated. The number of one- and two-stage processes is also different for each perceived word. It should be noted here that the execution time of just the same cognitive task (word recognition in particular), varies considerably and unpredictably from trial to trial even in short experiment.

Fig. 3. Variations of word recognition time for one subject during a single experiment. Red dots highlight the events presented in Fig1 and Fig4. Red numbers indicate the duration of each process in milliseconds.

Fig. 4. A) One-stage 173 ms long recognition process of the word *zavitoj-curlled*, observed in 20 sensors. The oscillation episodes which precede and follow recognition are highlighted in grey to enhance visibility. B) Recognition process of the word *kurchavyj-curly*, observed in 17 sensors. It runs during 762 ms in two stages highlighted in green and magenta. Red frames indicate magnetometer chips where signals from two crossed sensors were recorded.

Fig.3 illustrates this instability. The data presented in Fig1 and Fig.2 corresponds to the event with nearly average recognition time for this experiment (402 ms). There we see both one-stage and two-stage processes. On the other hand, very quick and very slow recognitions display different signal behavior, shown in Fig.4. During quick recognitions we see just one-stage signal, while slow events occur in two stages.

4. Discussion

Direct monitoring of the oscillatory activity of the brain, without averaging and statistical processing, provides a different look at how the cognitive tasks are executed. Perception of words is traditionally considered as a gradually (in hundreds milliseconds) developing process in the cortex, spreading from primary auditory areas into the integrative cortical association areas. MEG measurements, which average cortical responses across about hundred trials, seem to support this widely accepted point of view [10]. Our experiments indicate a different scenario for word perception. Monitoring raw brain signals we see that at the instant, when the subject starts to hear sound of the word, several distant from each other cortical areas abruptly switch their oscillation regime. First of all, this means that information about the word sound onset is quickly transmitted over almost the entire surface of the cortex. It is likely that such widespread broadcast of the initial alert occurs only when the subject has been assigned a specific task and is ready to perform it. The observed switch of the oscillation mode is presumptive indicator of the involvement of this neural population into perception process – the large group of neurons stays tuned to the incoming sound of the word. We also observe that in more than 10 sensors this oscillation mode persists up to just the instant when the subject presses the button, confirming recognition of the word heard. This holds for recognition events that run in one stage as shown in Fig.1. Simultaneous one-stage oscillation episodes in several different neural populations are the most salient feature of quick word recognition processes. It is important, that all these oscillation events terminate together just at the instant, when the task is completed. It is tempting to speculate that it is just the coordinated activity of this set of neural populations that leads to the decision on which word the subject heard. At the onset of word recognition, an acoustic signal activated this set of agents that solved the problem and in the end they together evoked a key press.

At the same time we see another set of neuronal populations that complete an episode together, earlier than the one-stage group, without evoking a key press. Presumably, they did not collect enough “votes” to make decision and are forced to start a new oscillation episode. Later this additional episode terminates simultaneously with the one-stage group and hence activity of a larger group of neural populations is synchronized. This is sufficient to make a decision. This group behaves like a traditional neural network, where signals from many neurons converge on a single one, and when their number is sufficient the target neuron is activated.

Delay in making decisions is a common phenomenon, discussed in [11] and called the process of procrastination. This is like a second round of voting if a convincing result was not achieved in the first round. The synchronous termination of oscillation episodes in many different cortical sites produces nerve impulses converging on the executive zone of the motor cortex, where the finger movement is initiated.

To achieve synchronization, neural populations scattered over the cortex must obviously exchange information about their running state and the expected time left to complete the task. We can speculate that the information transfer is similar to the behavior of a bee, dancing with characteristic wobbles along a certain path in the hive, informing her relatives about the distance to the flower meadow and the direction of movement. The signal shape during oscillation episode resembles this dance.

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6. References

1. A.Ya.Kaplan (1998). EEG nonstationarity: methodological and experimental analysis. *Advances in Physiological Sciences*, 29 № 3, 35-55. (Uspehi fiziologicheskikh nauk, in Russian).
2. Perotti L, DeVito J, Bessis D, Dabaghian Y. (2019) Discrete Structure of the Brain Rhythms. *Sci Rep*. 2019 Jan 28;9(1):1105. doi: 10.1038/s41598-018-37196-0. PMID: 30692564; PMCID: PMC6349927.
3. Vvedensky, V., Filatov, I., Gurtovoy, K., Sokolov, M. (2023). Alpha Rhythm Dynamics During Spoken Word Recognition. In: Kryzhanovsky, B., Dunin-Barkowski, W., Redko, V., Tiumentsev, Y. (eds) *Advances in Neural Computation, Machine Learning, and Cognitive Research VI. NEUROINFORMATICS 2022. Studies in Computational Intelligence*, vol 1064. pp. 65-70. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-19032-2_7.
4. Vvedensky V, Verkhlyutov V, Gurtovoy K (2024) Extended and distant cortical areas coordinate their oscillations approaching the instant of decision making during recognition of words. In: *Biologically Inspired Cognitive Architectures 2023 - Proceedings of the 14th Annual Meeting of the BICA Society. Studies in Computational Intelligence*, Samsonovich, A.V. and Liu, T. (eds) vol. 1130, pp. 956-961. Springer Cham doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-50381-8_103
5. Tadel, F., Baillet, S., Mosher, J.C., Pantazis, D., Leahy, R.M. (2011). Brainstorm: A User-Friendly Application for MEG/EEG Analysis. *Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience*. vol. 2011, ID 879716. doi:10.1155/2011/879716.
6. Vvedensky, V.L., Gurtovoy, K.G. (2021) Topology of the Thesaurus of Russian Adjectives Revealed by Measurements of the Spoken Word Recognition Time. In *Advances in Neural Computation, Machine Learning, and Cognitive Research IV. Neuroinformatics 2020. Studies in Computational Intelligence*, eds. Kryzhanovsky, B., Dunin-Barkowski, W., Redko, V., Tiumentsev, Y. vol. 925, 85-90. Springer, Cham. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-60577-3_9.
7. Vvedensky, V., Filatov, I., Gurtovoy, K., Sokolov, M. (2023). Alpha Rhythm Dynamics During Spoken Word Recognition, in: *Advances in Neural Computation, Machine Learning, and Cognitive Research VI. Neuroinformatics 2022. Studies in Computational Intelligence*, eds. Kryzhanovsky, B. et al., vol. 1064, 65-70. Springer, Cham. doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-19032-2_7.

8. Huth, A.G., de Heer, W.A., Griffiths, T.L., Theunissen, F.E., Gallant, J.L. (2016) Natural speech reveals the semantic maps that tile human cerebral cortex. *Nature*, 532, 453-458. doi:10.1038/nature17637.
9. Neymotin SA, Barczak A, O'Connell MN, McGinnis T, Markowitz N, Espinal E, Griffith E, Anwar H, Dura-Bernal S, Lytton WW, Jones SR, Bickel S, Lakatos P. (2022) Detecting spontaneous neural oscillation events in primate auditory cortex. *eNeuro* 29 July 2022, 9 (4) ENEURO.0281-21.2022; : <https://doi.org/10.1523/ENEURO.0281-21.2022>.
10. Pykkänen L, Marantz A. (2003) Tracking the time course of word recognition with MEG. *TRENDS in Cognitive Sciences* Vol.7 No.5, 187-189.
11. Sinha N, Brown JT, Carpenter RH. (2006) Task switching as a two-stage decision process. *J Neurophysiol.* 95(5):3146-53. doi: 10.1152/jn.01184.2005. Epub 2006 Feb 8. PMID: 16467422.